

THE IMPORTANCE OF FAIRY TALES IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO YOUNG LEARNERS

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Abstract: The article discusses about the role of fairy tales in teaching and learning English to secondary school students. It also emphasizes the functions of using fairy tales in the classroom, as well as, the ways of using them effectively. It is also discussed that fairy tales can provide a wealth source for making English classroom full of entertainment and enjoyment.

Key words: fairy tales, scenario, authentic materials, vocabulary, literature, atmosphere, wealth source.

Introduction

It is not always possible to teach English in a way that all students will make learning process full of enjoyment and fun. However, a teacher tries to make lessons interesting in order to have more effective and productive results in teaching. Particularly, learning a foreign language is a challenging process, it requires hard work and practice.

The role of fairy tales in teaching

There are a lot of motivating and effective methods and approaches in teaching English. However, fairy tales are suggested to be used in a classroom to create an amusing atmosphere with a great deal. Fairy tales are considered as wise and wealth sources for learning. As Lazar supports, “Literature provides wonderful source material for eliciting strong emotional responses from our students” and using it in classroom is “a fruitful way of involving the learner as a whole person”³¹

It is true that, a motivating and amusing work with fairy tales may contribute to make teaching easier and more efficient. With the help of fairy tales, all integrated

³¹ Lazar, Gillian. 1993. Literature and Language Teaching. Great Britain: Cambridge University Press.

skills of English can be provided with full of wealth possibilities. It can also include many English topics as well as with their conclusions. Tolkien adds “The clear and happy ending, good atmosphere, the sudden joyous turn and miraculous grace” are the ingredients of creative learning and teaching.³² As fairy tales has several magical scenes, fairy tales have on the development of children’s personality. Each scene teaches something new to young learners in order to make conclusion what is good or bad for them.

Moreover, with the help of fairy tales, learners can acquire different new vocabularies, especially authentic ones. Due to the fact that the stories of fairy tales are derived from the real-life scenarios, most of new words and phrases in tales are considered as authentic vocabulary materials in teaching. If learners can see and feel this scene, they can remember the word and its meaning to use them in practice.

There some techniques of using fairy tales in English classroom environment;

1. Create a mystical atmosphere with your body language, voice and lighting if possible.

As a teacher, reading fairy tales requires to use your body languages showing your emotions. Moreover, your tone of voice should be clear and colorful with different heroes of tales.

2. Don’t over do the scary characters with very young learners.

If English learners are too young to listen the tales, teachers should take characters` personality into consideration. Because, they can’t be afraid.

3. Involve the children as much as possible. Get them guessing the next episode throughout the story.

Teacher should avoid reading fairy tales only, instead, teachers should give a chance for their students to guess the next episode by asking their opinions.

4. You don’t need to systematically pre-teach vocabulary. Arouse their interest?

Asking new vocabulary should be fun in learning process. For instance, 'Is this the wicked witch or the friendly fairy?' 'Does the princess look sad or happy?' etc.

³² Tolkien, J. R. R. 1966. *The Tolkien Reader*. Chapter: On Fairy-Stories. New York: Ballantine Books.

You can go back over vocabulary after the story e.g. 'Can you remember what this is called?' (pointing to the picture).

5. Don't use it just as a time filler.

Try to make fairy tales as short as well as interesting. Otherwise, students can be boring of listening the story and learning.

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